

Supplementary Information: Accuracy in near-perfect virus phylogenies

JOEL O. WERTHEIM, MIKE STEEL, AND MICHAEL J. SANDERSON

MATHEMATICAL RESULTS AND PROOFS

Definitions and preliminary observations

Let $B(n)$ denote the set of unrooted binary phylogenetic trees with leaf set $[n] = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Thus, $B(n) = (2n - 5)!!$. Note that a tree $T \in B(n)$ has $2n - 3$ edges. Consider a Jukes-Cantor model in which all edges have the same value of λ . Thus, the probability of a state change between the endpoints of an edge e , denoted p_e , is given by $p_e = p$ where $p = \frac{3}{4}(1 - \exp(-4\lambda/3))$.

A *character* refers to the assignment of states to the taxa at a given site of an alignment. Let us say that a character evolves ‘perfectly’ on T if there is a single change of state across one interior edge (say e) and no change of state any other edge of T . The probability that this occurs for any given interior edge e is: $p_e \prod_{e' \neq e} (1 - p_{e'}) = p(1 - p)^{2n-4}$. Note that this probability does not depend on the particular choice of e or on the shape of T . Note also that a perfectly evolved character has at least two species present in each state (otherwise the change would have been on a pendant edge of T).

We will say that a character f evolves on T with c edge changes on e_1, \dots, e_c if state changes occur on edges e_1, \dots, e_c and on no other edge of T . More briefly, we say that f evolves on T with c edge changes if f evolves with c edge changes for some set of c distinct edges of T (mostly we will deal with the case $c = 2$). The probability that a character evolves on T with 2 edge changes on e_1, e_2 is $p^2(1 - p)^{2n-5}$, while the probability

20 that a character evolves on T with 2 state changes is $\binom{2n-3}{2}p^2(1-p)^{2n-5}$.

21 We pause here to make an observation: If a data set consists of characters each of
 22 which have evolved on T with either 1 or 2 edge changes, then the maximum parsimony
 23 tree(s) and the maximum compatibility tree(s) for this data set will be exactly the same.
 24 Moreover, if there are sufficiently many constant characters, then any maximum likelihood
 25 tree will also be one of these trees.

26 Recall that a *split* refers to a bipartition of the leaf set $[n]$ into two non-empty
 27 subsets (and splits are induced by binary characters). A character that has evolved
 28 perfectly on T produces a split, and these splits (across a set of perfectly evolved
 29 characters) are compatible and so form a (generally unresolved/non-binary) tree on leaf set
 30 $[n]$.

31 Now suppose that m characters evolve on T and suppose that, of these m
 32 characters, k of them are perfectly evolved on T (note that more than one of these
 33 characters may correspond to the same split of T).

34 Next, consider a single additional character f which has evolved on T with two edge
 35 changes on e_1, e_2 (there is no restriction that these are interior edges). The probability that
 36 this character f is a binary character is $\frac{1}{3}$ (as noted earlier). Moreover, in that case, the
 37 bipartition induced by f corresponds to a split of T if and only if e_1 and e_2 are adjacent.

38 The question now arises as to whether we can discover that f gives a false split of T
 39 (without knowing T), just on the basis of the other k perfectly-evolved characters.

We next introduce some further notation. We will let ξ denote the expected number
 of state changes in the tree T per character, under the model described. Thus ξ equals the
 per-edge rate λ times the number of edges of T , and so

$$\xi = \lambda \cdot (2n - 3).$$

40 We will also use the following standard notation throughout: we write $f(n) \sim g(n)$
 41 if the ratio $f(n)/g(n)$ tends to 1 as n becomes large.

42 Given a tree $T \in B(n)$, let $d_T(e_1, e_2)$ denote the number of edges of T that lie

43 strictly within the path between e_1 and e_2 (i.e. excluding e_1 and e_2). Thus, e_1 and e_2 are
 44 adjacent if and only if $d_T(e_1, e_2) = 0$

45 Next, given $T \in B(n)$, let $\varphi_T = (\varphi_T(0), \varphi_T(1), \dots, \varphi_T(n-3))$ where $\varphi_T(i)$ is the
 46 number of (unordered) pairs of edges $\{e, e'\}$ of T for which $d_T(e, e') = i$. Thus
 47 $\varphi_T(0) = 3(n-2)$, however the other values comprising φ_T depend on the shape of T . In
 48 particular, for a complete balanced binary tree with $n = 2^h$ leaves we have $\varphi_T(i) = 0$ for all
 49 $i \geq 2 \log_2(n) - 2$, while for a caterpillar tree with the same number of leaves we have
 50 $\varphi_T(i) > 0$ for all $i \leq n-3$.

51 Note that the sequence φ_T is a topological invariant (i.e. it depends only on the
 52 unlabelled shape of the tree) and does not depend on any other parameters mentioned
 53 above. Clearly, for any $T \in B(n)$ we have:

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-3} \varphi_T(i) = \binom{2n-3}{2}, \quad (1)$$

54 since both sides of this equation count the number of pairs of edges of T . For i between 1
 55 and $n-3$, we will let

$$\tilde{\varphi}_T(i) = \frac{\varphi_T(i)}{\binom{2n-3}{2}}. \quad (2)$$

56 Thus, Eqn. (1) translates to the identity $\sum_{i=1}^{n-3} \tilde{\varphi}_T(i) = 1$. Thus $\tilde{\varphi}_T(i)$ is the probability
 57 that a pair on edges (selected uniformly at random from all pairs) has exactly i edges lying
 58 on the path strictly between the two selected edges.

59 Next we state a simple combinatorial result that will be useful in the proof of the
 60 first theorem.

61 **LEMMA 1** Let f be a binary character that has evolved on T by 2 edge changes on e_1 and
 62 e_2 , and let f' be a character that has perfectly evolved on T by a change on a single
 63 interior edge e . Then f and f' are compatible (i.e. induce compatible splits) if and only if e
 64 does not lie on the path in T that is strictly between e_1 and e_2 (i.e. the red edges in Fig. 1).

65 *Proof:* First suppose that e lies on one of the red edges shown in Fig. 1, say between

66 t_i and t_{i+1} for $i \in \{1, \dots, r-1\}$. Let x_j be a leaf of t_j for $j \in \{0, i, i+1, r+1\}$. Then if f is
 67 a binary character arising from changes on (just) e_1 and e_2 then f splits the set
 68 $\{x_0, x_i, x_{i+1}, x_{r+1}\}$ as $x_0x_{r+1}|x_ix_{i+1}$ while f' splits this same set as $x_0x_i|x_{i+1}x_{r+1}$. Since
 69 these two partial splits are incompatible, so too are f and f' .

70 Next suppose that e lies in one of the green subtrees of Fig. 1 (including the stem
 71 edge of that subtree), say subtree t_i for $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, r+1\}$. We consider the possible
 72 cases: (1) $e \in \{e_1, e_2\}$, or (2) e is an edge of t_0 or t_{r+1} or (3) e is an edge of t_i or its stem
 73 edge for $i \in \{1, \dots, r\}$. Let $X_i \subset [n]$ denote the subset of leaves of T that are leaves of t_i .

74 In case (1), it suffices by symmetry to consider the case $e = e_1$. Then f' induces the
 75 full split $X_0|([n] - X_0)$ while f induces the full split $(X_0 \cup X_{r+1})|([n] - (X_0 \cup X_{r+1}))$ and
 76 these two splits are compatible, since the set on the left of the first split is contained in the
 77 set on the left of the second split.

78 In case (2), it suffices by symmetry to consider the case where e is an edge of t_0 . In
 79 that case f' induces a full split of the form $Y|([n] - Y)$ where $Y \subseteq X_0$, and this split is again
 80 compatible with the full split $(X_0 \cup X_{r+1})|([n] - (X_0 \cup X_{r+1}))$ induced by f since Y is a
 81 subset of the left part of this split.

82 In case (3), suppose that e is an edge of t_i or its stem edge. In that case, f' induces
 83 the split $W|([n] - W)$ where $W \subseteq X_i$, and since $X_0 \cup X_{r+1} \subseteq [n] - W$ it follows that f is
 84 compatible with f' . This completes the proof of Lemma 1. \square

85 Next, let $\Phi_T^{(k)}$ be the probability that a character f that has evolved on T with 2
 86 edge changes has the following three additional properties:

- 87 **(C-i)** it is a binary character,
- 88 **(C-ii)** the corresponding split is not a split of T , and
- 89 **(C-iii)** the split described by f is compatible with k characters that are perfectly evolved
 90 on T (by the Markovian process described above).

91 The point of these conditions is that we might add the split corresponding to f to

92 the other k compatible splits which still be compatible, but create a ‘false positive’ split in
 93 the resulting tree (note that we do not know a-priori which splits are the perfectly evolved
 94 ones, as we are assuming that T is not known).

95 We now present an exact expression for $\Phi_T^{(k)}$. Firstly, let \mathcal{C}_T be the collection of all
 96 (unordered) pairs of non-adjacent edges in T . Thus $|\mathcal{C}_T| = \binom{2n-3}{2} - 3(n-2)$. For
 97 $\{e_1, e_2\} \in \mathcal{C}_T$, let

$$R_T(e_1, e_2) = \frac{d_T(e_1, e_2)}{n-3}, \quad (3)$$

98 Thus $R_T(e_1, e_2)$ is the proportion of interior edges of T that lie between two
 99 non-adjacent edges e_1 and e_2 .

Fig. 1. A representation of T determined by the pair $\{e_1, e_2\}$ on which changes of state occur for character f . When f is a binary character, a perfectly evolved character f' will be compatible with f provided f' corresponds to a change of state on an edge in the green portions of the tree; otherwise, if the change is on one of the $r-1$ edges marked in red, the two characters will be incompatible.

100 Next, let μ_T denote the average value of $d_T(e, e')$ over all pairs of edges $\{e, e'\}$
 101 sampled from T . That is:

$$\mu_T = \frac{1}{\binom{2n-3}{2}} \sum_{\{e, e'\}} d_T(e, e'). \quad (4)$$

102 THEOREM 2 For each $T \in B(n)$, and $k \geq 1$ we have:

(i)

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_T^{(k)} &= \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\binom{2n-3}{2}} \cdot \sum_{\{e_1, e_2\} \in \mathcal{C}_T} (1 - R_T(e_1, e_2))^k, \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{n-3} \tilde{\varphi}_T(i) \left(1 - \frac{i}{(n-3)}\right)^k. \end{aligned}$$

(ii)

$$\Phi_T^{(k)} \geq \frac{1}{3} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\mu_T}{n-3}\right)^k - \frac{1}{(2n-3)}.$$

103 *Proof: Part (i):* Under the Jukes-Cantor model, the (conditional) probability that a
 104 randomly evolved character f is binary, given that it has evolved on T with 2 edge changes
 105 is $\frac{1}{3}$. To see this, let e_1, e_2 denote the two edges on which there are state changes. Then if
 106 the state at the left-hand end vertex of e_1 (as shown in Fig. 1) is α and the state on the
 107 right end vertex of e_1 is β then for f to be a binary character we require e_2 to involve the
 108 transition from β back to α (which is one of the three possible other states that β can
 109 change to on e_2 , and each change has equal probability under the Jukes-Cantor model).

110 Now consider a single random character f' that has perfectly evolved on T . Since
 111 (a) each of the $n - 3$ interior edges of T has the same probability of being the ‘change
 112 edge’ associated with f' , and (b) f' is compatible with f if and only if the associated
 113 change edge for that character does not lie on the path that is (strictly) between e_1 and e_2
 114 (by Lemma 1) and (c) the proportion of interior edges of T that do not lie strictly between
 115 the edges e_1 and e_2 is $1 - R_T(e_1, e_2)$, it follows that the probability that f' is compatible
 116 with f is $1 - R_T(e_1, e_2)$.

117 Thus, for k characters that have independently perfectly evolved on T the
 118 probability that each of them is compatible with f is $(1 - R_T(e_1, e_2))^k$.

119 Finally, each choice for f across all pairs of edges of T (nor just the non-adjacent
 120 pairs) has equal probability, and if we let $\eta(e_1, e_2) = 1$ if $\{e_1, e_2\}$ are not adjacent, and 0
 121 otherwise, then the probability that f satisfies properties (C-i), (C-ii) and (C-iii) above is

122 the average value of $\frac{1}{3} \cdot \eta(e_1, e_2) \cdot (1 - R_T(e_1, e_2))^k$ across all $\binom{2n-3}{2}$ pairs of edges $\{e_1, e_2\}$ of
 123 T , which gives the first expression in Theorem 2(i), and the second expression follows
 124 directly.

125 *Part (ii).* Let $Q_T^{(k)} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-3} \tilde{\varphi}_T(i) \left(1 - \frac{i}{n-3}\right)^k$. Then $Q_T^{(k)}$ is the expected value of
 126 $(1 - R_T(e_1, e_2))^k$ when a pair of edges of T is selected uniformly at random from the set of
 127 all such pairs. Since $f(x) = (1 - x)^k$ is a convex function, Jensen's inequality then gives:

$$Q_T^{(k)} = \mathbb{E}[(1 - R_T(e_1, e_2))^k] \geq (1 - \mathbb{E}[R_T(e_1, e_2)])^k = (1 - \mu_T)^k. \quad (5)$$

128 Now $\Phi_T^{(k)} = \frac{1}{3} \left(Q_T^{(k)} - \frac{3(n-2)}{\binom{2n-3}{2}} (1 - 0)^k \right)$, since there are $3(n - 2)$ pairs of adjacent edges in
 129 T , and $\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{3(n-2)}{\binom{2n-3}{2}} = \frac{1}{(2n-3)}$, and so applying this to the Eqn. 5 gives the result claimed.

130 □

131 **Remarks:** Theorem 2(i) shows that for fixed k and n , the shape of T plays a
 132 significant role in determining $\Phi_T^{(k)}$; in particular, pectinate trees (such as caterpillars) will
 133 have a smaller value of $\Phi_T^{(k)}$ than more balanced trees. Indeed, it is possible to exactly
 134 calculate the value of $\Phi_T^{(k)}$ for the two extreme families: caterpillars and fully-balanced
 135 trees to determine the extent of this dependence, as we describe in the next section. Notice
 136 also that the exact computation of $\Phi_T^{(k)}$ for a given tree T with n leaves involves a
 137 summation of just $O(n^2)$ terms, so could be calculated fairly easily.

138 Notice also that in the special case where $k = 1$, Theorem 2(i) simplifies (via
 139 Eqn. (1)) as follows.

Corollary 1

$$\Phi_T^{(1)} = \frac{1}{3} \left(1 - \frac{\mu_T}{n-3} \right).$$

140 *Exact values of $\Phi_T^{(k)}$ for classes of trees*

141 Proposition 1

(i) Let T_n denote a caterpillar tree with n leaves. Then $\Phi_{T_n} = 0$ and for $n \geq 5$:

$$\Phi_{T_n}^{(k)} = \frac{4}{3(2n-3)(n-2)(n-3)^k} \sum_{j=1}^{n-4} (j^{k+1} + j^k)$$

Thus, for fixed k we have:

$$\Phi_{T_n}^{(k)} = \frac{2}{3(k+2)} + o(1),$$

142 where $o(1)$ is a term that tends to 0 as n grows.

143 (ii) Let T^h denote any tree in $B(2^h + 1)$ obtained by attaching a leaf to the root of a
144 complete balanced binary tree of height h . Then

$$\varphi_{T^h}(i) = P(i, h) + Q(i, h), \quad (6)$$

where:

$$P(i, h) = \begin{cases} 2^{i+2}(2^{h-i} - 1), & \text{if } i < h; \\ 0, & \text{if } i \geq h \end{cases}$$

and

$$Q(i, h) = 2^i \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{h-1} 2^{h-j-1} S(i, j),$$

145 where

$$S(i, j) = \begin{cases} i - 1, & \text{for } 1 \leq i \leq j + 1; \\ 2j - (i - 1), & \text{for } j + 1 < i \leq 2j; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

146 (iii) Let \mathcal{D} be a probability distribution on $B(n)$. Then

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}}[\Phi_T^{(k)}] = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{n-3} \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}}[\tilde{\varphi}_T(i)] \left(1 - \frac{i}{(n-3)}\right)^k. \quad (8)$$

147 In particular, when \mathcal{D} is the PDA distribution on $B(n)$

$$\mathbb{E}_{PDA}[\tilde{\varphi}_T(i)] = \frac{(i+3)2^i(2n-i-4)!(n-2)!}{(2n-4)!(n-i-3)! \binom{2n-3}{2}}. \quad (9)$$

Proof: Part (i): For $n \geq 4$ any path of length ℓ in T_n that lies strictly between two edges $\{e, e'\}$ is a path of interior edges, and there are precisely four such pairs of edges that

correspond to the same path. Moreover, the number of interior edge paths of T_n of length $n - 3 - j$ is $j + 1$ for each j between 0 and $n - 4$. Thus,

$$\Phi_{T_n}^{(k)} = \frac{1}{3 \binom{2n-3}{2}} \sum_{j=0}^{n-4} 4(j+1) \left(\frac{j}{n-3} \right)^k,$$

148 and straightforward algebraic manipulation leads to the stated expression. The last part of

149 (i) follows from the asymptotic identity: $\sum_{j=1}^n j^k \sim \frac{n^{k+1}}{k}$.

150 *Part (ii)*

151 For $h \geq 1$, let U_i^h be the set of edges e of T^h , excluding the stem edge, for which
152 there are exactly $i \geq 0$ edges strictly between e and the stem edge. If we also let
153 $u^{(h)}(i) = |U_i^h|$ then it is easily seen that:

$$u_i^{(h)} = \begin{cases} 2^{i+1}, & \text{for } 0 \leq i \leq h-1; \\ 0, & \text{for } i \geq h. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

For $h \geq 1$ and $i \geq 1$, let N_i^h denote collection of pairs of edges in T^h that are separated by exactly i edges, and let $n_i^{(h)} = |N_i^h|$. Thus, $n_i^{(h)} = \varphi_{T^{(h)}}(i)$. Observe that:

$$n_i^{(h)} = 0 \Leftrightarrow i > 2h - 2.$$

154 Notice also that deleting the stem edge of T^{h+1} (and its incident vertices) produces two
155 copies of T^h - we will call these L and R ('left' and 'right').

156 The set N_i^{h+1} can be partitioned into three classes:

157 **Class 1:** A pair of edges consisting of an edge of T^{h+1} at distance i from the stem
158 edge, together with the stem edge. This set has size $u_i^{(h+1)}$, where $u_i^{(h)}$ is as given
159 above.

160 **Class 2:** A pair of edges that lie entirely within L or entirely within R . This set has
161 size $2 \cdot n_i^{(h)}$.

162 **Class 3:** A pair of edges $\{e_1, e_2\}$ with e_1 in L and e_2 in R with the distance between
163 e_1 and e_2 being i .

A little care is required to enumerate Class 3. One subcase is that e_1 is not the stem edge of L and e_2 is not the stem edge of R . In that case, the number of choices is

$$\sum_{(l,r) \geq (0,0): r+l=i-2, r, l \leq h-1} u_r^{(h)} u_l^{(h)},$$

which equals the expression $Q(i, h)$ given in Part (ii). The complementary subcase where e_1 or e_2 is the stem edge of L or R contributes

$$u_i^{(h+1)}.$$

Combining the above gives the recursion:

$$n_i^{(h+1)} = u_i^{(h+1)} + 2n_i^{(h)} + [Q(i, h) + u_i^{(h+1)}]$$

which simplifies to:

$$n_i^{(h+1)} = 2n_i^{(h)} + 2u_i^{(h+1)} + Q(i, h).$$

or equivalently,

$$n_i^{(h)} = 2n_i^{(h-1)} + 2u_i^{(h)} + Q(i, h-1).$$

164 Solving this recursion (noting that $u_i^{(h)} = 0$ for $i \geq h$) leads to the expression for
165 $\varphi_{T^{(h)}}$ given in Part (ii).

166 *Part (iii):* Eqn. (8) follows by linearity of expectation (and interchanging the order
167 of expectation operators).

The expression for $\mathbb{E}[\tilde{\varphi}_T(i)]$ involves an argument in enumerative combinatorics. Let $N(n, k)$ denote the number of (unordered) forests consisting of k rooted binary trees whose leaf sets are disjoint and contain a total of n leaves (we allow a single labeled leaf to be a rooted tree of size 1, otherwise the root of each tree has degree 2). It is easily seen that $N(n, 2)$ is precisely the number of rooted binary trees $(2n-3)!!$, since deleting the root of such a tree, produces a forest of two trees with disjoint leaf sets. It turns out there is an exact formula for $N(n, r)$ (from ~ 1990):

$$N(n, r) = \frac{(2n-r-1)!}{(n-r)!(r-1)!2^{n-r}},$$

168 for $r = 1, \dots, n$ (see e.g. (3), p. 105).

An *ordered forest* is a forest with a linear ordering on its component trees. If $O(n, r)$ denotes the number of ordered forests consisting of r trees then

$$O(n, r) = r!N(n, r) = r \frac{(2n - r - 1)!}{(n - r)!2^{n-r}}.$$

Notice that:

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{r=4}^n O(n, r) = (2n - 5)!! \times \left[\binom{(2n - 3)}{2} - 3(n - 2) \right].$$

169 To see this observe that twice the right-hand side counts the number of pairs $(T, (e_1, e_2))$
 170 where $T \in B(n)$ and (e_1, e_2) is an ordered pair of non-adjacent edges. Notice that if we
 171 delete the path connecting e_1 and e_2 we obtain an ordered forest of rooted trees on the
 172 same leaf set as T (cf. Fig. 1) . This provides a bijection between these two sets in which
 173 the number of strictly edges between e_1 and e_2 in T is equal to $i - 3$ where i is the number
 174 of forests.

Thus,

$$\varphi_T(i - 3) = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{O(n, i)}{(2n - 5)!!} = \frac{i2^{i-3}(2n - i - 1)!(n - 2)!}{(2n - 4)!(n - i)!},$$

175 and rearranging, gives the result.

176 □

177 To illustrate Part (i), with $n = 5$ we have $\Phi_{T_5} = \frac{8}{63}(\frac{1}{2})^k$. Notice that this converges
 178 to zero exponentially fast with k (and in general for fixed n this will be the case).

Also, observe that for general values of n and with $k = 1$ (say) we have:

$$\Phi_T^{(k)} = \frac{2(n - 4)}{3(2n - 3)(n - 2)} \left(1 + \frac{2n - 7}{3} \right).$$

179 Thus, for the simulation involving trees with $n = 500$ leaves, if these were caterpillars
 180 (instead of YH trees), for $k = 1$ we would expect $\Phi_T^{(k)}$ to be very close to $\frac{2}{9}$ (in agreement
 181 with the asymptotic claim in the Part (i) of Proposition 1) which is lower than the
 182 simulated values on YH trees, as expected.

To illustrate Part (ii), $\varphi_{T^3}(2) = P(2, 3) + Q(2, 3) = 2^4(2^1 - 1) + 2^2(2 + 1) = 28$.

Notice also that for general h we obtain (as expected)

$$\varphi_{T^h}(2h - 2) = 2^{2h-2},$$

183 and $\varphi_{T^h}(i) = 0$ for $i > 2h - 2$.

184 Notice that for h large, $P(i, h)$ is negligible relative to $Q(i, h)$.

185 *A lower bound on the expected value of $\Phi_T^{(k)}$ for the PDA and YH distributions*

186 **Proposition 2** Let T be a tree in $B(n)$ sampled from the PDA or YH distribution. Then,

187 for all $n \geq 4$ we have:

(i)

$$\mathbb{E}_{PDA}[\mu_T] = \frac{2}{(n-2)} \cdot \left[\frac{2^{n-2}n!}{(2n-3)!!} - 2n + 2 \right].$$

Moreover,

$$\mathbb{E}_{PDA}[\mu_T] = \sqrt{\pi} \cdot \sqrt{n} + o(1).$$

(ii)

$$\mathbb{E}_{PDA}[\Phi_T^{(k)}] \geq \frac{1}{3} e^{-k\sqrt{\pi}/\sqrt{n}} - o(1),$$

188 where $o(1)$ is a term that tends to 0 as n grows.

(iii)

$$\mathbb{E}_{YH}[\Phi_T^{(k)}] \geq \frac{1}{3} e^{-ck \log(n)/n} - o(1),$$

189 where $o(1)$ is a term that tends to 0 as n grows, and c is a constant (independent of
190 n).

191 *Proof: Part (i):* For $T \in B(n)$ let $NA(T)$ be the collection of (unordered) pairs
192 $\{e_1, e_2\}$ of non-adjacent edges of T .

193 The first step is to apply a classic technique in enumerative combinatorics; namely,
194 we count a certain set Ω in two different ways, to obtain an equation. Here, we take the set

195 Ω to be the collection of triples $(T, \sigma, \{e_1, e_2\})$ where $T \in B(n)$, σ is a split of $[n]$ that
 196 corresponds to an interior edge of T , and $\{e_1, e_2\} \in NA(T)$ with the edge of T
 197 corresponding to split σ being strictly within the path connecting e_1 and e_2 .

198 Summing first over all choices of T we have:

$$|\Omega| = \sum_{T \in B(n)} \sum_{\{e_1, e_2\} \in NA(T)} d_T(e_1, e_2). \quad (11)$$

199 and so,

$$\mathbb{E}_{PDA}[\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{C}_T}[R_T]] = \frac{|\Omega|}{|B(n)| \cdot |\mathcal{C}_T|}, \quad (12)$$

200 where $|\mathcal{C}_T| = \binom{2n-3}{2} - 3(n-2)$ is the number of pairs of non-adjacent edges in T .

201 On the other hand, we can count $|\Omega|$ by first summing over all choices of the split σ
 202 (stratified by the size k of the smaller half of the split) and then counting for each such σ
 203 the number of T and $\{e_1, e_2\}$. This gives:

$$|\Omega| = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n \binom{n}{k} [rb(k) \cdot rb(n-k)] \cdot [(2k-2) \cdot (2(n-k)-2)]. \quad (13)$$

204 where $rb(m) = (2m-3)!!$ is the number of rooted trees on a leaf set of size m .

205 To see this, note that $\binom{n}{k}$ is the number of ways to partition $[n]$ into a split σ of two
 206 sets of size k and $n-k$, and $\frac{1}{2}rb(k)rb(n-k)$ is the number of trees in $B(n)$ that contain
 207 this split (the factor $\frac{1}{2}$ is to remedy the double counting that occurs). Finally, given T and
 208 σ there are now $(2k-2)(2(n-k)-2)$ choices of $\{e_1, e_2\}$ where e_1 is an edge of the rooted
 209 subtree of T on the leaf set of size k and e_2 is an edge of the rooted subtree of T of size
 210 $n-k$.

We will apply generating function techniques to calculate an exact expression for
 term on the right hand side of Eqn. (13). Notice can rewrite Eqn. (13) as follows:

$$|\Omega| = 2n! [x^n] \sum_{k=1}^n \left((k-1) \frac{rb(k)}{k!} x^k \cdot (n-k-1) \frac{rb(n-k)}{(n-k)!} x^{n-k} \right)$$

211 where $[x^n]f(x)$ denote the coefficient of x^n in $f(x)$, and hence, even more compactly,

$$|\Omega| = 2n! [x^n] F(x)^2 \quad (14)$$

212 where

$$F(x) := \sum_{i \geq 1} (i-1) \frac{rb(i)}{i!} x^i. \quad (15)$$

213 Let $rb(n) = (2n-3)!!$ (the number of rooted binary trees on a leaf set of size n) and
 214 let $\nu(x) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{rb(n)}{n!} x^n$ denote the associated exponential generating function. It is well
 215 known (see e.g. (3)) that

$$\nu(x) = \frac{1}{2} \nu^2(x) + x \quad (16)$$

216 which has the unique solution

$$\nu(x) = 1 - \sqrt{1-2x}. \quad (17)$$

217 We will use the following relationships which follow easily from Eqn. (16):

$$\nu^2(x) = 2\nu(x) - 2x, \quad (18)$$

218

$$\nu(x)\nu'(x) = \nu'(x) - 1, \quad (19)$$

219 where $\nu'(x) = \frac{d}{dx}\nu(x)$.

Recall, $F(x)$ from Eqn. (15). We have:

$$F(x) = x\nu'(x) - \nu(x).$$

Thus,

$$F(x)^2 = x^2\nu'(x)^2 - 2x\nu(x)\nu'(x) + \nu^2(x),$$

220 and this simplifies by Eqns. (18) and (19)) to:

$$F(x)^2 = x^2\nu'(x)^2 - 2x\nu'(x) + 2\nu(x). \quad (20)$$

221 In order to determine the expression in Eqn. (14) we consider the coefficient of x^n in $F(x)^2$
 222 (i.e. $[x^n]F(x)^2$) by considering the three terms on the right of Eqn. (20). For the first term
 223 of Eqn. (20), Eqn. (17)) gives: $\nu'(x)^2 = \frac{1}{1-2x}$ and so

$$[x^n]x^2\nu'(x)^2 = [x^{n-2}]\nu'(x)^2 = [x^{n-2}](1-2x)^{-1} = 2^{n-2}. \quad (21)$$

224 For the second term of Eqn. (20), we have:

$$[x^n]2x\nu'(x) = 2[x^{n-1}]\nu'(x) = 2\frac{n \cdot rb(n)}{n!}. \quad (22)$$

225 For the third term of Eqn. (20), we have:

$$[x^n]2\nu(x) = 2[x^n]\nu(x) = 2\frac{rb(n)}{n!}. \quad (23)$$

226 Substituting the expressions on the right hand side of Eqns. (18), (19) and (20) into
 227 the corresponding terms in Eqn (20) allows us now to determine the expression for $|\Omega|$
 228 given by Eqn. (14), as follows:

$$|\Omega| = 2n! \left[2^{n-2} - 2\frac{n \cdot rb(n)}{n!} + 2\frac{rb(n)}{n!} \right]$$

229 which simplifies slightly to:

$$|\Omega| = 2 \left[2^{n-2}n! - 2(n-1)rb(n) \right]. \quad (24)$$

230 By substituting the expression for $|\Omega|$ given by Eqn. (24) into Eqn. (12) and rearranging
 231 terms, gives the claimed expression for $\mathbb{E}_{PDA}[\mathbb{E}_{C_T}[R_T]]$.

The second claim in Part (i) of Theorem 2 follows from the asymptotic equivalence:

$$\frac{rb(n)}{n!} \sim \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi}} 2^n n^{-3/2}$$

232 together with some standard algebraic manipulation.

Part (ii): We apply Theorem 2(Part (ii)) to Part (i) of the current theorem. With
 $k \leq \gamma\sqrt{n}$ we obtain:

$$\mathbb{E}_{PDA}[\Phi_T^{(k)}] \geq \frac{1}{3} \left(1 - \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{\sqrt{n}} \right)^{\gamma\sqrt{n}} \sim \frac{1}{3} \exp(-\gamma\sqrt{\pi}).$$

233 *Part (iii):* We apply Proposition 4 of (1) (where $\beta = 0$ corresponds to the YH
 234 distribution). This result shows that in a tree $T \in B(n)$ sampled according to the YH
 235 distribution the maximum distance D from any leaf to the root is less than

236 $(4.31 + \epsilon) \log(n)$ with a probability converging to 1 as n grows. Now μ_T is always less than
 237 twice the distance from any leaf in T to any other leaf in T , and this inter-leaf distances is
 238 bounded by $2D$. The result now follows from Theorem 2(Part (ii)). \square

239 **Remarks:**

240 Note that Parts (ii) and (iii) imply that for each fixed k , $\mathbb{E}_{PDA}[\Phi_T^{(k)}]$ and $\mathbb{E}_{YH}[\Phi_T^{(k)}]$
 241 both converge to $\frac{1}{3}$ as n grows, in contrast to the caterpillar case of Part (i) of
 242 Proposition 1, where the limit is smaller (e.g. for $k = 1$, the limit is $\frac{2}{9}$).

243 Notice also that the lower bounds on $\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}}[\Phi_T^{(k)}]$ allow k to grow faster with n for YH
 244 trees than PDA (essentially because in a Yule tree, there are on average fewer edges on
 245 paths between leaves, so fewer ‘red’ edges on the path between e_1, e_2 (see Fig. 1). In this
 246 lower bound we are undercounting by ignoring the red portions to the left of e_1 and right
 247 of e_2 by considering only cases where e_1 and e_2 are both pendant edges (this undercounting
 248 is valid since we are stating a lower bound on $\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}}[\Phi_T^{(k)}]$).

249 *The expected number of such false splits*

250 Note that Theorem 2 describes the probability that a single character satisfies the
 251 three conditions (C-i)–(C-iii) above, conditional on this character having evolved on T
 252 with 2 edge changes (thus $\Phi_T^{(k)}$ should be viewed as a conditional probability). This raises
 253 two further natural question: for a given character, what is the probability p_T that such a
 254 character will evolve so as to satisfy conditions (Ci)–(Ciii)? And how many such characters
 255 should we expect to see? For these questions, the number k of perfectly evolved characters
 256 should now be treated as a random variable, K . Thus, let K be the random variable
 257 corresponding to the number of distinct (and nontrivial) splits generated from those
 258 characters (from within the m characters in total) that have perfectly evolved on T . The
 259 variable K lies between 0 and m . Let μ_K be the expected value of K .

260 Conditional on $K = k$, the value p_T is simply given (ignoring terms involving λ of

261 higher than quadratic power) by:

$$p_T = \left[\binom{2n-3}{2} - 3(n-2) \right] \lambda^2 \Phi_T^{(k)}. \quad (25)$$

262 In particular,

$$p_T \sim 2n^2 \lambda^2 \Phi_T^{(k)}. \quad (26)$$

We have

$$\mu_K = (n-3) \left(1 - \left(1 - (\lambda + O(\lambda^2))^m \right) \right).$$

Provided that $\lambda m \ll 1$ we may approximate this last equation by:

$$\mu_K \approx (n-3) \lambda m.$$

Thus, provided that m large and $\lambda m < 1$ and using using μ_K to estimate K (which is reasonable since m is large, and we are also assuming above that $\lambda n \ll 1$) we obtain:

$$K \approx (n-3) \lambda m$$

and solving for λ in this equation, and substituting the estimate of λ into Eqn. (26) gives:

$$p_T \sim \frac{2K^2}{m^2} \Phi_T^{(K)}.$$

263 Let us now multiply through by m (the number of characters) to get.

$$mp_T \sim \frac{2K^2}{m} \Phi_T^{(K)}. \quad (27)$$

264 The term on the left (mp_T) has a natural interpretation - it is simply the expected
 265 number of characters that have evolved on T by 2 edge changes and that also satisfy the
 266 three conditions (C-i)–(C-iii) above. By Equation (27), this can be approximated by
 267 $\frac{2K^2}{m} \Phi_T^{(K)}$. Note that this quantity is independent of λ (provided this is sufficiently small
 268 that the above approximations are reasonable), and n also is not involved in the first term
 269 in the product.

270 Note that one cannot interpret mp_T as the expected number of false splits in a
 271 maximum compatibility tree involving the K perfectly evolved characters and the

272 additional characters with 2 changes. This is because some of these latter characters may
 273 be incompatible with each other (even though they are compatible with the K perfectly
 274 evolved characters).

275 *The case where $\ell > 1$ binary characters evolve with 2 edge changes on T*

276 So far we have considered the impact of a single binary character that has evolved
 277 on T with 2 edge changes. What happens if there is more than one such character? In
 278 particular, when will two such characters (which induce false splits) be compatible with
 279 each other? The following result provides a concise characterisation. This result is also
 280 relevant to case for more than two such characters, since a collection of binary characters is
 281 compatible if and only if every pair of characters is compatible.

282 **Proposition 3** Suppose that f and f' are two binary characters that have evolved on T ,
 283 each with with 2 edge changes (say e_1, e_2 for f and e'_1 and e'_2 for f'). Let P (respectively,
 284 P') denote the set of edges in the path in T consisting of e_1, e_2 (respectively e'_1 and e'_2) and
 285 the edges on the path between them. Then f and f' are compatible if and only if either
 286 one of the following two conditions holds:

287 (c_1) $P \subseteq P'$ or $P' \subseteq P$.

288 (c_2) e does not lie in P' and e' does not lie in P .

289 *Proof:* The proof involves a case analysis. In particular, we show that:

290 (1) if (c_1) holds then f and f' are compatible;

291 (2) if (c_1) fails but (c_2) holds, then f and f' are compatible; and

292 (3) if (c_1) and (c_2) both fail to hold, then f and f' are incompatible.

293 To simplify notation we first introduce some conventions. We will let σ (respectively
 294 σ') denote the split of $[n]$ induced by (reversing state) changes on e_1 and e_2 (respectively

295 on e'_1 and e'_2). For subsets V_1, \dots, V_r of $[n]$ we write $V_1 \cdots V_r | -$ as shorthand for the split
 296 $(V_1 \cup \cdots \cup V_r) | ([n] - (V_1 \cup \cdots \cup V_r))$, and if a subtree within T has leaf set $A \subset [n]$ we will
 297 denote this subtree by writing $t(A)$. We will also assume that e_1, e_2, e'_1, e'_2 are four distinct
 298 edges (we deal with the case where this fails at the end).

Fig. 2. The cases for the proof of Proposition 3

299 Case (1): Suppose that (c_1) holds. Without loss of generality we may assume that
 300 $P \subseteq P'$ and that the order of the path from e'_1 to e'_2 passes through e_1 and e_2 in this order.
 301 Thus we can represent T as in Fig. 2(i) where A, B, C, D, E denote the (unions of the) leaf
 302 sets of the corresponding subtrees determined by this arrangement of the four edges.

303 Thus σ is the split $ABDE|C$, and σ' is the split $AE|BCD$. Since the second half of
 304 he first split (namely C) is a subset of the second half of the second split (BCD) these two
 305 splits are compatible. Note that this argument also holds if one or both of the following
 306 identities applies: $e_1 = e'_1$ or $e_2 = e'_2$.

307 Case (2): Now suppose that (c_1) fails but (c_2) holds. In this case, by considering the
 308 path between e_1 and e_2 we can represent T as in Fig. 2(ii) and e'_1 and e'_2 either both lie the
 309 subtree $t(A)$ or $t(C)$ or else e'_1 lies in $t(B_i)$ and e'_2 lies in $t(B_j)$ for some i, j (we allow $i = j$)

310 First suppose that e'_1, e'_2 both lie within $t(A)$. Then $\sigma' = A'|-$ for a subset of A' of
 311 A and since $\sigma = AC|B$ these two splits are compatible. A similar argument holds if e'_1, e'_2
 312 both lie within $t(C)$. Alternatively, suppose that e'_1 is an edge in $t(B_i)$ and e'_2 is an edge of
 313 $t(B_j)$ (we allow $i = j$). Then $\sigma' = B'|-$ for a subset of B , and since $\sigma = AC|-$ these two
 314 splits are also compatible (since $B' \cap (A \cup C) = \emptyset$).

315 Case (3): Finally suppose that Case (c_1) and Case (c_2) both fail. Without loss of
 316 generality we may assume that e_1 lies within P' . In this case we can represent tree T as
 317 shown in Fig. 2(iii). Thus $\sigma' = (A \cup D)|-$.

318 By the assumption that Case (c_1) and Case (c_2) both fail, it follows that e_2 lies in
 319 one of the following trees $t(A), t(D), t(B_i)$, or $t(C_j)$, for some i, j . By symmetry, there are
 320 just two sub-cases to consider: (i) e_2 lies in $t(A)$ or (ii) e_2 lies in $t(B_i)$. In subcase (i)
 321 $\sigma = CDA'|-$ where A' is a proper subset of A , and C is the union of the leaf sets in
 322 C_1, \dots, C_s . Thus $\sigma = CDA'|-$ is incompatible with $\sigma' = AD|-$ since neither of the sets on
 323 the left of the split contains the other.

324 In subcase (ii), $\sigma = B'CD|-$ for a proper subset B' of B (the strict containment is
 325 because e_1 and e_2 are not adjacent) and so again σ and σ' are incompatible.

326 Finally, we assumed that e_1, e_2, e'_1, e'_2 are four distinct edges. Otherwise (since
 327 $e_1 \neq e_2$ and $e'_1 \neq e'_2$) we either have: $\{e_1, e_2\} = \{e'_1, e'_2\}$, in which case condition (c_1) holds,
 328 and the two characters f and f' induce the same split and so are compatible, or we may
 329 assume without loss of generality that $e_1 = e'_1$ and $e_2 \neq e'_2$. A similar (though simpler) case
 330 analysis to the above leads to the same conclusions as before.

□

331
 332 **Remark:** A consequence of Proposition 3 and our earlier results is that if n is large
 333 in comparison to k then a small number (ℓ) of 2-state characters evolved randomly on T
 334 are likely to be (i) compatible with each other, (ii) compatible with the k perfectly evolved
 335 characters, and (iii) not be splits of T , and thus show up as false splits on the
 336 reconstructed (max compatibility or max parsimony) tree. To see this, observe first that

337 the probability that (c_2) occurs tends to 1 as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for fixed k (this holds for any choice
 338 of T , or a randomly sampled tree from the PDA or YH distribution[†]. Second, a collection
 339 of binary characters is compatible if and only if each pair of them is compatible, and so if ℓ
 340 and k are fixed (or grow sufficiently slowly with n , depending on the tree shape) the
 341 probability that all ℓ false splits of T are present in the MP or MC tree (along with the
 342 splits corresponding to the k perfectly compatible characters of T) tends to 1 as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

343 ESTIMATING THE FALSE POSITIVE RATE

344 Given a binary phylogenetic tree T , and m characters evolved randomly on T by
 345 the model described earlier, the *false positive rate* (FP_T) is the expected value of the
 346 proportion of non-trivial splits in the reconstructed tree (using MC, say) that are not in T
 347 (here we assume that if the reconstructed tree is a star, this proportion (which is
 348 technically $0/0$) is zero). Recall that ξ is the expected number of state changes in the tree
 349 T per character, under the model described earlier. FP_T is a function of the three
 350 parameters T (specifically, its shape and number of leaves), m and λ (equivalently, FP_T is
 351 a function of T , m and ξ).

352 In general, it is mathematically complicated to describe FP_T in terms of these
 353 parameters. However, when the number of leaves in a tree grows faster than the number of
 354 perfectly compatible characters, it is possible to state a limit result, in order to provide an
 355 approximation to FP_T for large trees.

356 In the following theorem we consider the following setting:

357 I. $m\xi = \Theta(n^\beta)$ for some $0 < \beta < \frac{1}{2}$, and

358 II. $m\xi^2 = O(1)$,

359 where $O(1)$ refers to dependence on n (thus $m\xi^2$ is not growing with n). Note that
 360 Condition (I) implies that the number of perfectly-evolved characters grows with the
 361 number of leaves, but at a rate that is slower than linearly. When $\beta \geq \frac{1}{2}$, Condition (I) also

362 provides a positive probability that more than one perfectly-evolved character will give rise
 363 to the same non-trivial split. Conditions (I) and (II) imply that ξ decreases as n increases.

We will show that in this setting, the false positive rate is (asymptotically) of the form $\frac{\xi}{3}$ times a function Ω that involves T (via its shape), m and ξ . To describe this result, we need to define this function Ω . Let

$$\Omega(T_n, \xi, m) = \sum_{i=1}^{n-4} \tilde{\varphi}_{T_n}(i) \cdot \frac{e^{-i\mu/(n-3)} - e^{-\mu}}{1 - i/(n-3)},$$

where

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2}m\xi$$

364 and where $\tilde{\varphi}_{T_n}(i)$ is given in Eqn. (2). For example, for any caterpillar tree, we have
 365 $\tilde{\varphi}_{T_n}(i) = 4(n-2-i)/\binom{2n-3}{2}$.

366 Notice that $\Omega(T_n, \xi, m)$ depends on T_n only via the coefficients $\tilde{\varphi}_{T_n}(i)$, and this
 367 dependence is linear. Thus, if \mathcal{D} is a distribution on trees (e.g. the PDA or YH) then the
 368 expected value of $\Omega(T_n, \xi, m)$ is given by:

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}}[\Omega(T_n, \xi, m)] = \sum_{i=1}^{n-4} \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}}[\tilde{\varphi}_{T_n}(i)] \cdot \frac{e^{-i\mu/(n-3)} - e^{-\mu}}{1 - i/(n-3)}. \quad (28)$$

369 For the PDA distribution, the term $\mathbb{E}_{PDA}[\tilde{\varphi}_T(i)]$ has an explicit exact value, given
 370 by Eqn. (9).

371 **THEOREM 3** For each $n \geq 1$, let T_n be a binary phylogenetic tree with n leaves, and
 372 suppose that Conditions (I) and (II) hold.

(i)

$$FP_{T_n} = \frac{\xi}{3} \cdot \Omega(T_n, \xi, m)(1 + o(1))$$

373 where $o(1)$ is a term that tends to 0 as n grows.

(ii) If T_n is sampled from a distribution \mathcal{D} (e.g. PDA, YH) then the expected value of FP_{T_n} , denoted $\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}}[FP_{T_n}]$, satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}}[FP_{T_n}] = \frac{\xi}{3} \cdot \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}}[\Omega(T_n, \xi, m)](1 + o(1)).$$

374 (iii) If T_n is a caterpillar tree, then $FP_{T_n} = 4(1 + o(1))/(3m)$.

375 *Proof: Part (i):* For convenience, we will write T in place of T_n . The number X_1 of
 376 perfectly evolved characters on T has a binomial distribution (m trials, with the probability
 377 of success of $\frac{\xi}{2}(1 + o(1))$ (since the proportion of interior edge in T is $(n - 3)/(2n - 3) \sim \frac{1}{2}$)
 378 and so has expected value $\frac{1}{2}m\xi(1 + o(1))$). As before, let K denote the number of distinct
 379 non-trivial splits of T_n that correspond to (one or more) of these perfectly evolved
 380 characters. By Condition (I) it follows that each perfectly evolved character is (with
 381 probability $\rightarrow 1$) generated at most once, and so K is approximated by X_1 , which in turn
 382 is approximated (for large n) by a Poisson distribution with mean $\mu = \frac{1}{2}m\xi$.

383 Consider now the splits that arise from 2-edge-change characters on T . Denote the
 384 number of false splits by X_2 , and the number of true splits by X'_2 . The expected value of
 385 X'_2 is of order $m\xi^2/n$ and so it converges to zero as n grows, by Condition (II). By
 386 Proposition 3 and Condition (II), the probability that every pair of the X_2 false splits is
 387 compatible (with each other) tends to 1 as n grows.

388 Next, consider splits (true or false) that arise from characters involving 3 or more
 389 changes on different edges. If X_3 denotes the number of such characters, then the expected
 390 value of X_3 is bounded above by a constant (independent of n) times $m\xi^3$, and by
 391 Conditions (I) and (II), the ratio of this to K is of order ξ^2 (independent of n).

392 Thus,

$$FP_T = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\xi^2 m}{2} (1 + o(1)) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{n-4} \tilde{\varphi}_T(i) \sum_{k=0}^{n-3} \frac{\left(1 - \frac{i}{n-3}\right)^k}{k + O(1)} \mathbb{P}(K = k), \quad (29)$$

393 where K has a Poisson distribution with expected value $\mu = \frac{m\xi}{2}$, and $O(1)$ refers to
 394 a term that is bounded in n (by Condition (II)) and accounts for any non-trivial splits
 395 induced by characters that are not perfectly evolved and in the reconstructed tree (as well
 396 as for splits from perfectly evolved characters that are 'lost' in a strict consensus by being
 397 the only such split in a path between the two edges of a 2-change character), while $o(1)$
 398 refers to a term that tends to zero as n grows due to characters that involve 3 or more edge

changes).

Thus, $\mathbb{P}(K = k) = e^{-\mu}\mu^k/k!$, and so, under Conditions (I) and (II) we have:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-3} \frac{\left(1 - \frac{i}{n-3}\right)^k}{k + O(1)} \mathbb{P}(K = k) \sim e^{-\mu} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\rho\mu)^k}{k!(k+1)},$$

where $\rho := 1 - \frac{i}{n-3}$. We now apply the identity: $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^k}{k!(k+1)} = \frac{e^x - 1}{x}$, with $x = \rho\mu$ to obtain:

$$e^{-\mu} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\rho\mu)^k}{k!(k+1)} = e^{-\mu} \left(\frac{e^{\rho\mu} - 1}{\rho\mu} \right) = \frac{e^{\mu(\rho-1)} - e^{-\mu}}{\rho\mu} = \frac{e^{-i\mu/(n-3)} - e^{-\mu}}{(1 - i/(n-3))\mu}. \quad (30)$$

Since $\mu = m\xi/2$, notice that we can write the term $\frac{\xi^2 m}{2}$ in Eqn. (29) as $\xi\mu$ and so, from Eqns. (29) and (30), we have:

$$FP_T \sim \frac{1}{3}\xi\mu \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{n-4} \tilde{\varphi}_T(i) \frac{e^{-i\mu/(n-3)} - e^{-\mu}}{(1 - i/(n-3))\mu}. \quad (31)$$

Finally, canceling the term μ in the numerator and denominator on the right-hand-side of Eqn. (31) gives the expression in Part (i).

Part (ii): This follows directly from Part (i) by linearity of expectation.

Part (iii): When T_n is a caterpillar tree we have:

$$\tilde{\varphi}_{T_n}(i) = \frac{4(n-2-i)}{\binom{2n-3}{2}},$$

for $1 \leq i \leq n-3$. We can rewrite this as: $\tilde{\varphi}_{T_n}(i) = \frac{4}{2n-3} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{i}{n-2}\right)$, and substituting this into Part (i) we obtain:

$$FP_{T_n} = \frac{\xi}{3} \cdot \frac{4}{(2n-3)} \sum_{i=1}^{n-4} \left(1 - \frac{i}{n-2}\right) \cdot \frac{e^{-i\mu/(n-3)} - e^{-\mu}}{(1 - i/(n-3))} \cdot (1 + o(1)).$$

As $n \rightarrow \infty$ we have the asymptotic identity:

$$FP_{T_n} \sim \frac{\xi}{3} \cdot \frac{4}{(2n-3)} \sum_{i=1}^{n-4} (e^{-i\mu/(n-3)} - e^{-\mu}) \sim \frac{2\xi}{3n} \cdot \left(\left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} x_n^i \right) - (n-4)e^{-\mu} \right), \quad (32)$$

where $x := e^{-\mu/(n-3)}$.

Now, x converges to 1 from below as n grows (under Conditions (I) and (II)), and so applying the identity $\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} x^i = x/(1-x)$ (for $0 < x < 1$), together with the identity

410 $1 - x \sim \mu/(n - 3) \sim \mu/n = m\xi/2n$ (since $\mu = \frac{1}{2}m\xi$) gives:

$$FP_{T_n} \sim \frac{2\xi}{3n} \cdot \frac{2nx_n}{m\xi} - (2\xi/3)e^{-\mu} \sim 4/(3m), \quad (33)$$

411 noting that the term $(2\xi/3)e^{-\mu}$ is asymptotically negligible relative to the term it follows
 412 in Eqn. (33) under Conditions (I) and (II). This completes the proof.

413

□

414

APPENDIX 1: LINKS BETWEEN ML AND MP

415

Given $T \in B(n)$ and a data set D consisting of a sequence of m characters. Let n_i
 416 be the number of these characters that have parsimony score i on T , for $i \geq 0$ (thus n_0 is
 417 the number of constant-state characters present in the data, n_1 is the number of characters
 418 present that could have perfectly evolved on T etc). We will assume that (i) each character
 419 has a unique most-parsimonious representation on T and (ii) no edge is involved in a state
 420 change for more than one character (under a most-parsimonious representation on T).

421

These conditions are reasonable under conditions (1) and (2) described earlier for
 422 large n , where $n_0 \gg n_1 \gg n_2 \dots$ and where m grows more slowly than n so changes on
 423 edges are likely to be ‘well-spaced’. We consider a likelihood setting where an edge counted
 424 by n_i has probability p_i and an edge not used in any most parsimonious reconstruction has
 425 probability ν .

Note that

$$\sum_{i=0}^k n_i = m \text{ and } \sum_{i=1}^k i n_i = ps(T, D),$$

426

where $ps(T, D)$ is the parsimony score of the tree T for the data. We will assume that

427

$ps(T, D) \ll m$.

428

Now, we can write the likelihood function for T as follows:

$$L(T|D) = Q_0^{m-n_0} \cdot Q_1^m \cdot q_1^{n_1} q_2^{2n_2} \dots q_k^{kn_k}, \quad (34)$$

where $Q_0 = \nu^{2n-3-ps(T,D)}$, $Q_1 = \prod_{i=1}^k (1 - p_i)^{in_i}$, $q_i = \frac{p_i}{1-p_i}$. Clearly, $L(T|D)$ is maximised by
 setting $\nu = 1$ (regardless of the other parameters). Moreover, the log likelihood critical

values for p_i obtained by solving the equations:

$$\frac{\partial \ln(L)}{\partial p_i} = 0,$$

429 gives $p_i = \frac{1}{m-n_0}$ for all $i \geq 1$; in particular, the optimal p_i values are all equal, and applying
 430 Eqn. (34) shows that $L(T|D)$ is then a monotone decreasing function of $ps(T, D)$. In this
 431 case, as noted in (2) (p. 353), the MP tree(s) maximize this optimal likelihood score.

432 APPENDIX 2: THE PROBABILITY A FALSE SPLIT DOES **not** APPEAR

433 Now consider any given binary tree T , a character f that has evolved on T by 2
 434 edge changes on e_1, e_2 , together with k perfectly evolved characters on T (with all the
 435 characters independently evolved under the Jukes-Cantor model with p_e constant across
 436 the edges of T).

437 Let $\Psi_T^{(k)}(e_1, e_2)$ be the probability that f satisfies conditions (C-i) and (C-ii) above
 438 (i.e. it is binary, and corresponds to a split that is not in T), and this split does **not** occur
 439 in either the MP (or MC) tree for the data that consists of f together with k perfectly
 440 evolved characters. In the case of ties (in constructing the MP or MC tree) these are
 441 broken uniformly.

Proposition 4 Then:

$$\Psi_T^{(k)}(e_1, e_2) = \frac{1}{3} \left(1 - (1 - R_T(e_1, e_2))^k - \frac{1}{2} k R_T(e_1, e_2) (1 - R_T(e_1, e_2))^{k-1} \right).$$

442 *Proof:* Let \mathcal{B} be a binomial random variable consisting of k trials, with the
 443 probability of success on each trial of $R_T(e_1, e_2) = \frac{d_T(e_1, e_2)}{n-3}$ (as defined earlier). Then
 444 $\Psi_T^{(k)}(e_1, e_2) = \frac{1}{3} (1 - \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{B} = 0) - \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{B} = 1))$. The factor of 1/2 is to allow for the breaking
 445 of a tie when $\mathcal{B} = 1$ between the two MC (or MP) trees. □

446 Observe that if e_1 and e_2 are adjacent, then $R_T(e_1, e_2) = 0$ and so $\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{B} = 0) = 1$ and
 447 thus $\Psi_T^{(k)}(e_1, e_2) = 0$.

448 Next, let $\Psi_T^{(k)}$ be the expected value of $\Psi_T^{(k)}(e_1, e_2)$ across all pairs of edges $\{e_1, e_2\}$.
 449 Thus, $\Psi_T^{(k)}$ is a natural quantity to compare with the earlier $\Phi_T^{(k)}$. We then have:

Corollary 2

$$\Psi_T^{(k)} = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\binom{2n-3}{2}} \cdot \sum_{\{e_1, e_2\} \in \mathcal{C}_T} \left[1 - (1 - R_T(e_1, e_2))^k - \frac{1}{2} k R_T(e_1, e_2) (1 - R_T(e_1, e_2))^{k-1} \right].$$

450 **Remark:** Notice that $\Phi_T^{(k)}$ is a monotone decreasing function of k (and thus
 451 $\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}}[\Phi_T^{(k)}]$ is also). Also, since we can write $\Psi_T^{(k)} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{B} \geq 1) + \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{B} \geq 2))$ it follows that
 452 $\Psi_T^{(k)}$ is a monotone increasing function of k (and so $\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}}[\Psi_T^{(k)}]$ is also).

453 Notice also that

$$\Phi_T^{(k)} + \Psi_T^{(k)} \leq \pi_n \tag{35}$$

454 and

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} (\Phi_T^{(k)} + \Psi_T^{(k)}) = \pi_n, \tag{36}$$

455 where $\pi_n = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{3(n-2)}{\binom{2n-3}{2}} \right)$ is the conditional probability that a character f is binary and
 456 that the split induced by this binary character is incompatible with T given that f has
 457 evolved on T with 2 edge changes. To see this, observe that there are $\binom{2n-3}{2} - 3(n-2)$
 458 pairs of non-adjacent edges in T , all 2 edge change characters have the same probability.
 459 Eqns. (35) and (36) also apply if Φ and Ψ are replaced by their expected value over a tree
 460 distribution \mathcal{D} .

REFERENCES

- 461
- 462 Aldous, D. (1995). Probability distributions on cladograms. In: Random Discrete
 463 Structures, eds. D. Aldous and R. Pemantle, 1-18. Springer: IMA Volumes in
 464 Mathematics and its Applications 76.
- 465 Goldman, N. (1990). Maximum likelihood inference of phylogenetic trees, with special
 466 reference to a Poisson process model of DNA substitution and to parsimony analysis.
 467 Syst. Zool. 39(4):345–361.
- 468 Steel, M. (2016). Phylogeny: Discrete and random processes in Evolution. SIAM.

Fig. 3. Mean expected false positive rate in the near-perfect zone of $\xi \leq 1$ for three different breadths of MP tree search algorithm for a PDA distribution of trees (1,10, and 100 random addition sub-replicates per simulation replicate; 1000 simulation replicates). Predicted values from Eqn. 2 (main text) is given by dashed line.

Fig. 4. Effect of across-site-rate variation on expected false positive rate for MP inference for different values of the α_{ASR} shape parameter of the ASR gamma distribution. Smaller α values have higher rate variation. Edge length variation is assumed absent. Dashed curve is the prediction from Eqn. 2 (main text), in which both sources of variation are absent. Tree search algorithm has 100 subreplicates per simulation replicate; 1000 simulation replicates.

Fig. 5. Effect of model complexity on expected false positive rates for MP. JC69 model (open circles) corresponds to near-perfect assumptions in shaded box ($\xi \leq 1$). HKY model (closed triangles) has a transition:transversion ratio of 5 and equal base frequencies. HKY+ASR+EL model (closed diamonds) has a transition:transversion ratio of 5 and also rate variation across sites ($\alpha_{ASR} = 1$) and edges ($\alpha_e = 1$). Points are means of 1000 replicates \times 100 sub-replicates.

Fig. 6. Mean false positive rate in the near-perfect zone of $\xi \leq 1$ for maximum likelihood searches in IQTree2 using different search breadths and corrections. Each point is the mean in 500 replicate simulations with a PDA distribution of trees. Open plusses: one subreplicate search per simulation replicate; open triangles: one subreplicate plus 3-state correction; open circles: 10 subreplicate searches plus 3-state correction and trees combined via strict consensus. closed squares: 100 subreplicate searches plus 3-state correction and trees combined via strict consensus. The “3-state correction” collapses edges less than $1/m$ substitutions per site, prior to consensus ($m = 1000$ sites). For comparison to theory for MP, predicted values from Eqn. 2 are given by dashed line.

Fig. 7. Five measures of clade support estimated on perfect four-taxon trees as alignment length varies. Each edge of the tree has exactly one site with a substitution on that edge; all other sites are constant. Support metrics using bootstrap resampling are denoted with solid shapes.

(A) Symmetric Trees

Fig. 8. Measures of clade support estimated on perfect trees of different sizes and alignment lengths. Each edge of the tree has exactly one site with a substitution on that edge; all other sites are constant. (A) Simulations on perfectly symmetric trees. (B) Simulations on perfectly asymmetric (caterpillar) trees. SH-aLRT in red, aBayes in blue, Ultrafast bootstrap in gray, traditional bootstrap in black, and transfer bootstrap exchange (TBE) in open gray circles.